

DEVELOPING EFL STUDENTS SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH TASK-BASED INSTRUCTIONS.

IMPORTANCE OF DIALOGUES AND MONOLOGUES TO DEVELOP STUDENTS SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract—The primary purpose of this study was to identify students' perception about the implementation of peer dialogue to improve speaking ability. The study operated the quantitative approaches which include survey research. This research takes the students of speaking class in English Education Department. The sample was taken from 32 females and 4 males in a class. The data was collected using questionnaire that talk about peer dialogue to improve speaking ability. Results of this study interpret students' perception of peer dialogue to improve speaking ability.

Keywords: speaking ability, communication, peer dialogue

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is widely considered to be an important skill most people wish to be really good at. While language becomes a tool for communication and speaking skill is a vitally important method of communication. We use language in the variety of situations, for example, workers in their workplace, families at their homes, or even students in their colleges are supposed to speak correctly and effectively in order to communicate well with one another. Speaking has received much attention in the last several years, especially in the English teaching and learning process. Students at school are not only asked for knowing the language itself but also they have to be able to apply it through communication. Students must have capacity to put words together in a meaningful way to reflect thoughts, opinions, and feelings. Many activities are provided by the teachers to stimulate students speaking skills, for instance, having a presentation, discussion, speech, debate and others. Therefore, the main focus of English class is using the foreign language as to communicate regardless of accuracy; as a consequence, oral communication becomes the cornerstone in the classroom (Gordillo Santofimia, 2011, p. 1). In the next few years, speaking will become an important thing for people's career success.

A common problem of speaking English in English classroom course is students are afraid to practice speaking with others. They will feel the anxiety when having a conversation with others using foreign language, or they will have difficulties in finding partners for having a speaking conversation. Based on professional found several factors that became problems and make students confused and difficult to speak English, among the problems that are possessed by students is difficult in their pronunciation or expression. Many students who do not know how to pronounce the vocabulary correctly, so students also confused with based on their opinion and the explanation from the teacher. Even some of them also confused about the vocabulary that they have. There are also some students who have difficulty in speaking is due to having a minimum vocabulary. Therefore, students are very passive in speaking skill in English. Therefore, students must practice the skill in speaking as the researcher before, that speaking is an ability must be practiced a lot and students can use speaking using ways such

as speaking in front of the mirror or can practice with a friend. Another similarity problems happened in students in UINSA. From the problems occurred, speaking becomes an ability that must be practiced a lot and one of the strategies to practice speaking is using peer dialogue.

Some studies have been carried out about the use of peer- dialogue for improving students speaking skill. Rika Mulya investigated the use of pair work technique to improve students speaking skill with 60 high school students in Banda Aceh as the participants. In her research, she compared the test result of two classes as experimental and control class, and she found that pair work technique is effective for improving students speaking performances. In addition, Ahmad and Yusuf (2014) in their research reported the students' pair work interaction to develop the students speaking skills in an ELT classroom which consists of international learners. Their research concluded that pair work interaction could effectively develop the students speaking skill if the teacher can pair the students with mixed

speaking proficiency. Moreover, Raquel Sánchez Ruiz (2016) also argued the peer dialogue project could help children to speak in public since at the beginning, some of them had stage panic, which progressively disappeared. Previous works have only focus on comparing the students' test speaking result with peer-dialogue approach and without it but failed to address on how the perceptive of students about peer – dialogue as a way to improve students' speaking skill. This case has motivated the researcher to carry out this study.

Therefore, this present paper seek to address how students' perception of peer dialogue to improve students speaking ability. It will explore deeper on how the peer dialogue strategy could increase students fluency speaking skill. The objective of this study are to identify the effect of peer dialogue to improve students' speaking ability, to identify the level of student's speaking ability in UINSA and to know the necessity of implementing peer dialogue in speaking English class

A. Peer Dialogue

Peer dialogue becomes one of the ways to improve students speaking ability. Based on University of Newcastle definition about peer dialogue, it defined that Peer dialogue as structured conversations between peers regarding learning and teaching. Swain 1997 added that the type of dialogue interaction explored in education can be regarded as a collaborative dialogue. In collaborative dialogue, learners work together to solve linguistics problems and construct language or knowledge about language. Language mediates this process-as a cognitive tool to process and manage meaning-making; as a social tool to communicate with others.

Besides, this dialogue is very important to give students the opportunity to speak English in class and can help them overcome their nervousness when they speak English "(Rahmawati & Pd, 2013). So Dialogue is the right technique in improving speaking skills if teachers and students can apply it well. B on those definitions, it can be concluded that peer dialogue is having a conversation or deep communication between two or more people in the classroom that include theab o listen and share views with each other.

Speaking

Speaking is one of the skills that have to be mastered by the students in learning English. Speaking is commonly used in many purposes; communication, debate, and others. According to Byrne (1984), speaking is an oral communication. Speaking is an interactive process that occurs between the speaker and listener. It involves the productive and receptive understanding skill, while Huebner (1969) states that speaking is the important skill in communication. Based on this idea, it can be concluded that through speaking, someone will get ease and fluency in

communicating with one another. Rivers (1978:162) says through speaking people can express the contents of their minds or communicate the ideas that have been react to other person or situation. Furthermore, people can express what they want from others and response to other speakers. It means that to express their ideas to the listener, the speaker must concern the aspect of speaking needed so that the message can be accepted and understood by the listener.

Furthermore, speaking is the action of delivered information, expressing thoughts and feeling. Such as (Alfi, 2015) cited that Thornbury (2005: 20) states that speaking is an activity in real life that is carried out by speaker to carry out his/ her ideas to interact with listeners. The activities are unplanned and their continuity is based on situations. Then, (Qureshi, n.d.) said that a language is a tool for communication. So, we are using language to communicate with others, to express our ideas, and to know others' ideas as well. Based on Higgs & Clifford (1982:221) stated that, speaking as one of the four macro skills is necessary for effective communication in any language, particularly when speakers are not using their mother tongue. Speaking is used for many different purposes, and each purpose involves different skill.

References:

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